

Neurological disorders in infants may represent a potential risk factor for the development of atopic dermatitis

Distúrbios neurológicos em lactentes podem representar um fator de risco potencial para o desenvolvimento de dermatite atópica

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ABSTRACT

Background: Central nervous system injuries can trigger some cellular systemic inflammatory reactions, which can also express receptors for neurotransmitters, neuropeptides, and neurotrophins. Thus, epilepsy, neuropsychiatric problems, stress, attention deficit disorders, hyperactivity, and autism spectrum disorders may be associated with some immune-mediated diseases, like atopic dermatitis. We aimed to investigate a possible link between neurological disorders caused by neonatal brain injuries with atopic dermatitis and high IgE levels in infants. **Methods:** Infants at risk of neurological disability, including structural brain injury detected by transfontanellar ultrasound (SCITU), intraventricular hemorrhage and secondary hydrocephalus, periventricular leukoencephalomalacia, and neonatal asphyxia, were included. Bayesian analysis was performed. Infants who presented with neurological disorders, atopic dermatitis, or exposure to environmental allergens were identified, and IgE levels were measured. **Results:** Seventy-four patients completed the study. Thirty infants (40%) presented atopic dermatitis. Patients with neurological disorders had a higher risk of presenting with atopic dermatitis compared to patients without neurological disorders (RR 3.23 95% CI 1.68-6.19). Patients with SCITU also had a higher risk of developing atopic dermatitis compared to patients without SCITU (RR 1.78 95% CI 1.23-2.56). Relative risk of atopic dermatitis was also higher in patients exposed to environmental allergens (RR 3.72 95% CI 1.76-7.87). No differences were found in IgE levels between the compared groups. **Conclusion:** These findings suggest a potential link between neurological disorders with atopic dermatitis and high IgE levels, highlighting a possible bidirectional communication between central nervous system and the immune system.

Keywords: Atopic dermatitis, Immunoglobulin E, Neurological disorders, Neuroimmunomodulation, Infants.

RESUMO

Introdução: Lesões no sistema nervoso central podem desencadear reações inflamatórias sistêmicas que podem expressar receptores para neurotransmissores, neuropeptídeos e neurotrofinas. Conseqüentemente, condições como epilepsia, transtornos neuropsiquiátricos,

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estresse, transtornos de déficit de atenção, hiperatividade e transtornos do espectro autista podem estar associadas a doenças mediadas pelo Sistema imunológico, como a dermatite atópica. Este estudo teve como objetivo investigar uma possível ligação entre desordens neurológicas causadas por lesões cerebrais neonatais e dermatite atópica, juntamente com altos níveis de imunoglobulina E (IgE) em lactentes. Métodos: O estudo incluiu lactentes em risco de deficiência neurológica devido a lesões cerebrais estruturais detectadas por ultrassonografia transfontanelar (SCITU), hemorragia intraventricular e hidrocefalia secundária, leucoencefalomalácia periventricular e asfixia neonatal. Foi realizada uma análise bayesiana para identificar lactentes com desordens neurológicas, dermatite atópica ou exposição à alérgenos ambientais e níveis de IgE. Resultados: Setenta e quatro pacientes completaram o estudo, sendo que trinta lactentes (40%) apresentaram dermatite atópica. Pacientes com desordens neurológicas tiveram um risco maior de desenvolver dermatite atópica em comparação com aqueles sem tais desordens (RR 3,23; IC 95% 1,68-6,19). Além disso, pacientes com SCITU também tiveram um risco maior de desenvolver dermatite atópica em comparação com aqueles sem SCITU (RR 1,78; IC 95% 1,23-2,56). O risco relativo de dermatite atópica também foi elevado em pacientes expostos a alérgenos ambientais (RR 3,72; IC 95% 1,76-7,87). Não foram encontradas diferenças significativas nos níveis de IgE entre os grupos comparados. Conclusão: Esses achados sugerem uma possível ligação entre desordens neurológicas e dermatite atópica com níveis elevados de IgE, indicando uma possível comunicação bidirecional entre o sistema nervoso central e o sistema imunológico.

Palavras-chave: Dermatite atópica, Imunoglobulina E, Desordens neurológicas, Neuroimunomodulação, Lactentes.

INTRODUCTION

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is the most frequent chronic inflammatory skin disease, whose incidence has increased in recent decades. Although AD can manifest at any age, the disease occurs within the first six months of life in 45% of cases and approximately 60% of all cases begin during the first year of life. Children living in urban areas are the most affected¹. AD signs include chronic or recurrent xerosis, pruritic eczema involving flexural and extensor areas and cutaneous infections. Immediate skin test reactivity and elevated total IgE can be found in up to 80% of patients².

Although the pathophysiology of AD is not completely understood, some studies demonstrated that skin barrier dysfunction and immune dysregulation contribute to the pathobiology of AD. Besides that, some risk factors have been identified, such as exposure to environmental allergens (EA), family history for allergy, use of antibiotics in pregnancy and cesarean delivery^{3,4}.

Neurological disorders (ND) are a set of abnormalities, usually occurring in early

life, that involve a generalized commitment of motor function, among others. ND can result from brain structural abnormalities, such as intraventricular hemorrhage, hydrocephalus secondary to intraventricular hemorrhage, and periventricular leukomalacia, which usually occur in preterm infants and are detected by transfontanelar ultrasound. Perinatal asphyxia is also a cause of ND and can occur in neonates of any gestational age⁵. Central nervous system (CNS) injuries can activate some inflammatory cells, such as lymphocytes, macrophages, and antigen-presenting cells, which express receptors for neurotransmitters, neuropeptides, and neurotrophins. These cells play an important role in antigen recognition during early phases of immune response, as well as in cellular effector functions that actually trigger allergic processes⁶.

While a link between the nervous system and the immune system is recognized, it is still not well understood, particularly in early life when these critical systems are developing. However, growing epidemiological data suggests complex and bi-directional interactions between

neuropsychological wellbeing and immune disorders, which are increasingly relevant with the dramatic rise in inflammatory immune diseases such as allergy and autoimmunity. There is some evidence that epilepsy, neuropsychiatric problems, stress, attention deficit disorders, hyperactivity, and autism spectrum disorders may be associated with some immune-mediated diseases like AD⁷⁻⁹.

Some experiments indirectly revealed the existence of an intricate network of bidirectional communications between the CNS and the immune system. These communication pathways are present at different levels of organization. At the local level, there is clear evidence for the production and use of immune factors by the CNS and for the production and use of neuroendocrine mediators by the immune system. Proinflammatory cytokines produced by the immune system, such as IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α , influence mood, cognition, memory, and social behavior. Conversely, neuroendocrine pathways—particularly the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis—modulate immune responses negatively by releasing cortisol, a glucocorticoid with potent immunosuppressive effects¹⁰.

In this setting, we aimed to evaluate a possible association between ND caused by neonatal brain injuries with AD and high IgE levels in infants.

METHODS

Study design and patients

This prospective study was carried out between July 2017 and December 2019 at the Hospital Gineco-Obstétrico Isidro Ayora, a tertiary care hospital in Ecuador, and the San Juan de Jerusalen Center, Ecuador. These are specialized centers for detecting and treating patients with ND in infants.

The inclusion criteria were infants from birth to 18 months of life; neonatal asphyxia and brain structural injury detected

by transfontanellar ultrasound (SCITU): leukoencephalomalacia according to the Volpe classification¹¹; intraventricular hemorrhage according to the Vries classification¹²; and hydrocephalus secondary to intraventricular hemorrhage. Transfontanellar ultrasound was performed by a specialist on all patients. Patients with ND were divided into two groups: with AD and without AD. AD was diagnosed according to the criteria proposed by Hanifin and Rajka¹³.

The exclusion criteria were infection by human immunodeficiency virus, congenital syndromes and malformations. Patients were withdrawn from the study if they discontinued follow up or death.

Study procedure

Infants with AD suspicion were referred to dermatologist for diagnosis confirmation and underwent a blood collection for total IgE measurement. The patients without AD were evaluated for IgE measurement between 9 and 12 months of age.

Total IgE was quantified by electrochemical luminescence standardized according to the manufacturer (Cobas 8000, Switzerland) and expressed in IU/mL. Serum level ≥ 15 IU/mL was considered high.

Medical charts were reviewed based on the following data: family history for allergy, type of delivery, exposure to antibiotics, and breastfeed. Nutritional status was evaluated according to the World Health Organization. Fenton curves were used for preterm infants; birth weight was expressed in grams (g) and presented as mean and standard deviation (SD).

Statistical analysis

Bayesian statistical models were used as they are robust against outliers, allow taking into account and deviations from normality assumptions, and allow decisions

to be made based on objective criteria, such as the region of practical equivalence (ROPE) around the null value of a given parameter. A first Bayesian model was used to estimate the relative risk (RR) as a measure of association between the risk of AD and some variables of interest. A second Bayesian model considered the IgE levels as a continuous dependent variable and groups of interest as a dummy independent variable (infants with and no ND, SCITU, AD, or EA exposure). So the results allow mean comparisons as in a conventional t-test. In this case, the ROPE indicates a small range of parameter values that are considered to be practically equivalent to the null value (equality of means). A Monte Carlo method based on Markov chains (MCMC) was used to fit both Bayesian models to the data, simulating posterior distributions for the parameters of interest. A total of 50,000 iterations were run for each parameter, with the first 1000 discarded to avoid the influence of initial conditions on parameter estimation (burn-in sampling). Highest probability density intervals (HDI) were obtained from the posterior distributions of the parameter using non-informative priors. HDI are the Bayesian analogue of the frequentist confidence intervals (CI). If the HDI excludes the ROPE, the model rejects

the null value. Effect size was measured by the standardized difference between two means, or $\text{mean (group 1) - mean (group 2) / standard deviation}$. The code for data processing were those presented by Kruschke¹⁴. Data analysis was performed using JASP and the R Project for Statistical Computing 3.3.6¹⁵, including the jags and coda packages¹⁶.

Ethical considerations

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and the International Conference on Harmonization Good Clinical Practice guidelines. The Ethics Committee of Hospital Eugenio Espejo approved this study. Parents or legal guardians signed a written informed consent.

RESULTS

Description of patients

One hundred and thirty patients were enrolled in the study and 74 completed the 18-month follow-up (Figure 1).

Patients were stratified according to the presence of ND at hospital discharge.

Figure 1. Flowchart of patients' recruitment.

Table 1 shows the demographic characteristics of the 74 patients who completed the study.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Final Sample.

Characteristic	Value
Gestational age (weeks)	25 to 41
Gestational age (mean)	35.3
Weight at birth (mean), gs	2134
Cesarean section (n, %)	45 (61%)
Females (n, %)	34 (46%)
Malnutrition at one year old (n, %)	19 (25%)
Prenatal antibiotics exposure (n, %)	42 (56%)
one cycle	33 (44%)
two cycles	9 (26%)
Neonatal antibiotics exposure (n, %)	45 (60%)
one cycle	25 (34%)
two to four cycles	20 (27%)
Relatives with allergies (n, %)	42 (57%)
Breastfed status at age 1 year	35 (47%)

Evaluation of AD

AD was diagnosed in 30 patients (40%). A significant association was observed between the presence of AD and ND (Bayesian RR of 3.23, 95% CI: 1.68-

6.19). Table 2 shows the relative risk (RR) among patients with and no AD; with and no ND; with and no SCITU, and with and no EA exposure.

Table 2. Bayesian relative risk for AD.

Variables	Yes	No	RR (95% CI)
	n (%)	n (%)	
ND	19 (76)	6 (24)	3.23 (1.68-6.19)
No ND	11 (22)	38 (78)	
SCITU	25 (58)	18 (42)	1.78 (1.23-2.56)
No SCITU	5 (16)	26 (84)	
EA exposure	17 (81)	4 (19)	3.72 (1.76-7.87)
No EA exposure	13 (24)	40 (76)	

Assessment of IgE levels

Eleven of 74 patients (15%) presented IgE level ≥ 15 IU/mL. Among them, 10 patients (90%) presented AD.

Table 3 shows the means for IgE levels by variables of interest. We found a significant difference between infants with

and no ND, with and no AD, and with no EA exposure, as the Bayesian 95% CI did not include the ROPE (values closed to zero). However, no significant difference was found between the infants with and without SCITU, as the Bayesian 95% CI included the zero value.

Table 3. Bayesian estimates for the means of IgE levels by variables of interest (Bayesian 95% CI, difference of means, and effect size).

Groups	Mean (95%CI)	Difference of means (95%CI)	Effect size ^a (95%CI)
ND	8.24 (5.21 – 11.4)		
No ND	3.11 (2.28 – 3.99)	5.18 (1.18 – 8.23)	1.21 (0.35 – 2.3)
SCITU	4.93 (2.93 – 7.48)		
No SCITU	3.54 (2.42 – 4.99)	1.32 (-1.95 – 4.16)	0.39 (-0.26 – 1.01)
AD	3.10 (2.31 – 4.04)		
No AD	10.70 (6.70 – 15.30)	7.50 (3.51 – 12.20)	1.13 (0.48 – 1.97)
EA	9.34 (4.56 – 15.8)	6.11 (1.01 – 12.3)	0.87 (0.13 – 1.77)

^aThe effect size is given by $(\mu_2 - \mu_1) / \sqrt{(\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2) / 2}$ and is interpreted as the difference between the means relative to the standard deviation.

DISCUSSION

AD is the most common chronic inflammatory skin disease. Genetic and environmental factors contribute to the cutaneous inflammatory process. High total IgE level can be found in up to 80% of patients and up to 70% of patients have a family history of atopic diseases². Reports on the association between the prevalence of atopic diseases and ND have been scarce in the literature. We investigated a possible relationship between ND caused by neonatal brain injuries with AD and high IgE levels in infants. We observed a potential link between ND with AD and high total IgE levels in infants. Furthermore, the exposure to EA was an important factor to development of AD and sensitization in this group of patients. To our knowledge, this is the first clinical trial that evaluated the relationship between ND and AD with high levels of IgE.

In this study, the presence of ND was not different between sexes. In contrast to our findings, Smith et al.¹⁷ described an increased risk of neurological damage due to prematurity or asphyxia in male patients.

There are very few studies regarding the relationship between ND and DA. Qu et al.¹⁸ evaluated a total of 2580 children with different kind of ND and they found that children diagnosed with more than one type of atopic disease, including AD, were more likely to have a diagnosed ND. Meldrum et al.¹⁹ investigated the relationship between early allergic disease and sensitization at 12 months of age and ND and they showed that children with any diagnosed allergic disease had evidence of reduced motor scores, and this was most apparent for a diagnosis of AD. In this study, we found that 40% of the infants presented AD during the first year of life. However we have to point out some aspects. A higher number of children were delivered by cesarean section (60%). The high AD prevalence in developing countries over the last decades has been attributed to excess hygiene, which reduces the exposure of the immune system to microbes²⁰. Besides that, less than 50% of infants were breastfed. Early-life formula feeding can contribute to allergic disease development²¹. On the other hand different findings were described by other studies. Villareal-Parra²² found no difference in the

prevalence of AD in children and adults with cerebral palsy. Similar findings were obtained by Niño et al.²³, who evaluated children with hyperactivity disorder. Bjarnadóttir et al.²⁴ evaluated 650 children prospectively and they found that neurodevelopmental scores were unrelated to AD and persistent wheeze.

Regarding the association between infants with SCITU, AD and IgE levels, we found no significant difference in IgE levels. In this setting, we could not find studies in the literature to compare these results.

When IgE levels were compared between the groups, the Bayesian analysis showed higher immunoglobulin values in the ND, AD, and EA groups, suggesting that the exposure to EA may have a potential role in sensitization and development of AD. Similarly to our findings, Julvez et al. (2009)²⁵ evaluated preschool children and observed association among elevated IgE levels, allergic disorders and neurobehavioral alterations. Magalhães et al (2009)²⁶ investigated a group of patients with Asperger's syndrome and they found a high incidence of AD, allergic rhinitis, and asthma; in addition, 90% of these patients presented elevated levels of IgE.

The main strength of this study is that all patients were evaluated by the same researcher, providing early recognition of possible complications, allowing for more personalized care. This may have improved the accuracy of AD diagnosis. Moreover, very few clinical trials explored the relationship between ND and AD in infants.

This study has some limitations. We did not get a control group of healthy neonates. The skin prick test to determine sensitization to specific allergens was not performed. During the study period, it was not possible to perform nuclear magnetic resonance imaging in all patients. Despite the limitations, the present study provided some evidence suggesting a potential link between ND and AD. Further studies

evaluating the role of brain structural abnormalities on the immune response and development of allergic disease are needed.

CONCLUSION

This study suggests a potential interaction between the central nervous system and the immune system during early development, indicating a possible association between neonatal neurological injuries, atopic dermatitis, and elevated IgE levels in infants. These findings have significant implications for clinical practice, as identifying this potential relationship underscores the importance of a comprehensive approach in managing neurological and immunological disorders in infants, facilitating early detection and more effective treatment.

Furthermore, these results open new perspectives for future research on neuro-immunological interactions and their role in atopic disease development, which could lead to advancements in pediatric medical care and enhance the understanding of brain-immune system relationships during critical infant developmental periods.

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List of abbreviations:

AD: Atopic dermatitis
CNS: Central nervous system
CI: Confidence intervals
EA: Environmental allergens
HDI: Highest probability density intervals
IgE: immunoglobulin E
IU/mL: International Units per Milliliter
MCMC: Monte Carlo method based on Markov chains
ND: Neurological disorders
SCITU: structural brain injury detected by transfontanellar ultrasound
ROPE: Region of practical equivalence
RR: Relative risk
SD: Standard deviation

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